

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MBA****FIRST NAME: ANTHONY****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical format)

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

THE CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

A doctoral degree involves a lot of writing. The ability to write, especially in an academic international capacity, cannot be overemphasized. The strategic placement of the course, ACA-401D: International Academic Writing, as a gateway course into the doctoral program is worthy of note. Students going into the various graduate program are equipped with the necessary and essential writing skills for a successful graduate experience. For me, this is a very important course that is very fundamental to my success in my other courses and in my professional life generally

2) BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

The basics of essay writing is covered in the course pack for this period. The course pack materials are divided into two sections. The first section deals with the basics of essay writing, while the second section is lecture note on a variety of academic writing issues such as “What is an excellent paper?”, plagiarism, citations, paraphrasing, styles of writing – personal versus academic writing, to name a few. Understanding the basics of essay writing is very important. A good essay writing skill will follow six distinct steps:

a. Starting the essay.

It is important to start work early, define the questions, define the question and analyze the tasks, construct an initial plan, and draw up an initial essay plan (EUCLID 2015, 2).

b. Researching the topic.

Researching the topic involves reading for essay and make notes from the reading. Develop an initial essay plan (EUCLID 2015, 2).

c. Organizing your ideas.

Organize your ideas and review the initial essay plan. It is advisable to rewrite your initial essay plan (EUCLID 2015, 2).

d. Writing the essay.

Write a first draft of the essay to test the structure and framework of your essay. The structure of the essay should communicate your idea and answer to the question (EUCLID 2015, 3).

e. Referencing the essay.

All academic essays **must** have a reference (EUCLID 2015, 4).

f. Editing the essay.

Take time to edit your work. Review the essay and make the necessary corruption.

In the second part of the coursepack, lecture materials dealing with a variety of essay writing issues are covered. Prominent among them is the issue of plagiarism. Plagiarism is defined, and examples of it are given. Recommendations are given on how to cite sources and how to avoid plagiarism.

3) DOCUMENTING A RESPONSE PAPER

It is important to document a response paper. All response paper must be written using the EUCLID response paper template. Some of the basic rules of writing a response paper are:

- **Style** – The Style must be *Normal* and single-spaced (BASIC 00:12-0045).
- **References** – In-text formatting (Author *space* Year, Page) must be used. Footnotes are not used in response paper. Footnotes may be used for comments only (BASIC 00:51-17:34)
- **Language** - The use of US English locale is preferred, even though UK English is acceptable. It is not appropriate to use both locales in the same response paper (BASIC 00:51-17:34)

How to change/set language: 1. Open your Word document. 2. Do, Ctrl-A – to select entire document. 3. Select **Review**. 4 Select **Language**. 5. Select **Language**. 6. Select Proofing language. 7. Select your language of choice

- **Rules of style** – Rules of style deal with how to make citations and references - punctuations, numbers, capital letters, etc., A response papers must be single-spaced and periods (full-stop) may be placed using the US English convention, before the quotation mark (BASIC 00:51-17:34).
- **Table of Content** – may be generated from paragraph or documents headings (BASIC 00:51-17:34).
- **How to save** - A response paper may be saved using the canonical format (First Name, Last Name, Program Code, Period Number – *without the commas*) in Word format or PDF. (BASIC 00:51-17:34)
- **Document submission** – Once the document is ready for submission – send a copy to the instructor, and a copy to the IFC. (BASIC 00:51-17:34)

4) **CONCLUSION**

This first period of the first doctoral course in EUCLID is an important and detailed introduction into the very important topic of the essential concepts of academic writing, and EUCLID's course period structuring It is quite commendable that this course is placed as the gateway course for three reasons Firstly, it prepares and equips the student with the essential knowledge and techniques required for success in an academic program that is heavily dependent on a strong ability to engage in academic writing Secondly, the templates supplied with the courses removes guesswork, and makes for consistency among the various students Finally, the templates are world class best practices, and could be used in real life, academic and other writings I enjoyed this first period materials, and I truly believe that it has refreshed and has provided the necessary writing knowledge that would be necessary in other academic writings I must, however, comment that I had to supplement the very first section of the response paper I did not think that the material covered in this section

REFERENCES

“Basic ACA-401 Tutorial: Understanding Styles and Templates for ACA-401.
“LMS at www.eucliduniversity.net.

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.